

OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING COMPETENCE IN MEDICAL CULTURE AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLE WITHIN THE TRAINING OF THE FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Today, it is impossible not to recognize the importance of healthy lifestyle and its role in our lives, and how important the concept of medical culture is in our lives. What is the purpose of forming the competence of medical culture for the future teacher? What is the expected goal of forming the concept of medical culture for students studying internal medicine? We will try to find answers to such questions in this article.

Introduction

The health of children and adolescents is a matter of first-class importance in any society and in any social conditions. Because it is one of the dominant factors determining the future of the country. The gene pool of the nation, along with the scientific and economic potential of the society, as well as other demographic indicators, are a socially sensitive barometer of the country's economic development. For example, the state program of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the "Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" in the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy Development" on "Decree No. PF-5953 of March 2, 2020 and No. PF-6099 of October 30, 2020 "On Measures to Widely Implement a Healthy Lifestyle and Further Development of Mass Sports" in order to ensure its implementation, as well as to implement specific programs that help to strengthen the health of the population, to attract young people, women and the elderly to a healthy lifestyle, and to create additional conditions for increasing their physical activity The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers was approved. [1] It revealed the importance of a healthy lifestyle at the same time as education, as an integral part of our daily life. organization of events and propaganda work was launched in this regard. In recent years, in our country, practical work on the organization of the system in all areas and stages of the education system has reached a decisive high level based on modern requirements. Nowadays, the great changes in the field of education, all the created conditions encourage young students to step forward under one slogan towards a prosperous future, to serve for the development of the country, to make a greater contribution to its prosperity. Currently, it is an honorable responsibility of us teachers to raise future

pedagogues to be more educated, level-headed people who can be an example to others with their manners.

Main part

In the system of communication in the working process of pedagogues, the relationship between leaders and students-young people occupies a great place. In this process, students try to learn the knowledge and moral experience accumulated by mankind over the centuries. The teacher is the leading person in the educational process. It takes a lot of hard work, strength and perseverance for the pedagogues in the field of primary education to become skilled masters of their profession, and to become pedagogues who are capable of taking a place among the young souls who are educating and taking their first steps to school. Today, a pedagogue is a consultant psychologist who can give the right solution in any situation, a mature pedagogue who integrates education and training, who analyzes the processes of a child's physical and spiritual being. a medical worker should be able to be a close friend when the time comes.

At the threshold of the new millennium, in the turbulent period of socio-economic changes in society, the health of young children and attention to it has become a global issue. Children are our future, it is very difficult to imagine today and tomorrow without their joyful laughter. In this regard, it is very important for schoolchildren to know concepts such as healthy lifestyle and medical culture and apply them in life. What is the purpose of forming the competence of medical culture for the future teacher? Currently, most diseases are found in young children. The teacher himself must have medical competence on how to eliminate, prevent, and take measures in cases where urgent help is needed. We can list the following reasons for the formation of competence of medical culture.

1. An increase in the number of children, but a decrease in the number of people with the ability to work.
2. Observation and appearance of depression (depression, relaxation) processes regardless of age
3. The increase and spread of alcoholism, drug addiction, drug addiction, etc., and their impact on the young generation.
4. The occurrence and spread of AIDS (SPID) and HIV (HIV) infection. Today, it is observed not only in teenagers, but also in young children.
5. Increase in cancer, tuberculosis, diabetes, genital diseases, etc. . Today, it is observed not only in teenagers, but also in young children.
6. Iodine element distribution in the body. These cases are increasing over the years.
7. Lack of iron and other trace elements in the body. These cases are increasing over the years.
8. The occurrence of sexual impotence, even sexually impotent "sterile" children.
9. Increase in deaths. Regardless of age.
10. The development of murder and the increase of several other negative factors. This situation has also increased among school-age children.
11. Deterioration of ecological conditions and their damage to the human body.
12. Genetic defects, weakening of the immune system. and others.
13. Currently, the complications of the COVID-19 disease are observed more strongly in the elderly and young children than in middle-aged people.[2;245-B]

We can expand the list of reasons given above. But we have given the reasons for the problems that have affected accurate statistical data and are almost common today. Well, the reasons that cause problems for us are clear, why is the solution still not developed and used in practice? The changes in our health are related not only to the doctor, but the state of our body is a direct result of our daily activities. Today, we need to form the concept of medical culture in children from elementary school age. A pedagogue should influence the child with a psychological-pedagogical approach. In order to achieve a good result, the teacher needs pedagogical skills, the extent to which he has acquired knowledge in this field and is able to apply it correctly. What opportunities can a primary education teacher give us to form the competence of medical culture in children? For this, we can observe the formation of the following opportunities in children:

- trying to acquire healthy knowledge and skills
- strive to be healthy
- turning health into a personal value - achieving perfection from the point of view of health
- persuading to be the guardian of one's own health
- to create confidence in the child about the possibility of making a positive impact on the community, family, work or school, building a culture of healthy living in the neighborhood
- creates a number of opportunities, such as giving young people a pedagogical and psychological understanding of the coherence of concepts such as material and spiritual health of society, their duration and priority.

It is not an exaggeration to say that the stage of the formation of competence of medical culture is interrelated with several aspects, that is, philosophical, social and pedagogically independent concepts are connected to a certain extent. They are: concepts of health, lifestyle and culture.

Conclusion

In my opinion, with the joint efforts of parents, teachers, specialists, it is a very important issue to form the concept of a healthy lifestyle in children - as one of the main competencies of health care.

It is necessary to form and make habits of health care skills in children, to protect and strengthen health, to form competence of medical culture in children and to teach them to value health. The formation of ideas about the elementary rules of health care by the teacher as a result of the perception of the indicated movements of physical exercise complexes, morning hygienic gymnastics, visual aids and video materials will give an effective result.

From our research, we have seen that by introducing at least one element of health-preserving technologies into the lesson, it is possible to make the learning process both interesting and entertaining, to create a cheerful, hard-working mood in children, to facilitate overcoming difficulties in mastering educational material, and to increase interest. It is possible to achieve an increase. For this purpose, we will continue to work on this project, carry out research, and create and implement a special training manual focused on the pedagogical and psychological principles of increasing the competence of medical culture in future primary education teachers. I hope that I will be able to publish it.

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